

Supporting Information

Cs₂AgBiBr₆ Perovskites: Designing Stable, Sensitive and Selective Eco-friendly Ozone
Sensors

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Figure S1. Experimental setup.

Figure S2. EDS analysis of $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ microparticles of (a) sheet-, (b) faceted flower- and (c) spherical flower- shaped morphology.

Figure S3. (a) XRD patterns of microsheet- (red pattern), spherical microflower- (blue pattern) and faceted microflower- (magenta pattern) based sensors. The asterisks (*) indicate the reflections of the side phases AgBr (COD 9008596) and the circles (●) show the Cs₃Bi₂Br₉ crystal structure (ICDD 01-070-0493). (b-e) Absorbance spectra of all the microcrystals and (f) the indirect band gap energy calculated through Tauc plots for indirect bandgap semiconductors of the same samples.

Figure S4. FESEM images of $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ micro-sheets.

Table S1. O_3 sensing performance of different chemiresistive sensors.

Sensing material	Concentration (ppb)	Response ^a	Ref.
$\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ microsheets	168	1.07	This work
ZnO	30	44 (UV)	61
ZnO-gold	30	108 (UV)	61
InGaZnO	1000	13 (UV)	62
SnO_2 -ZnO	20	8 (UV)	59
6SnO_2 nanorods	500	3	65
1wt% AgIn_2O_3	100	1.58	56
0.1% Au/ TiO_2 - WO_3 (3:1)	2500	64 (LED)	63
NiAl	15	1.22	57
In_2O_3	10	4 (UV)	60
Au@ TiO_2	500	1.15 (RH% 50)	58
TiO_2 - In_2O_3	2000	56 (LED)	64
Carbon nanotubes	5000	1.3	53

^a Response = $R_{\text{gas}}/R_{\text{air}}$ or $R_{\text{air}}/R_{\text{gas}}$

Table S2. Metal halide perovskite ozone sensors at room temperature.

Sensing material	Concentration (ppb)	Response ^b	t _{res} (s)	t _{rec} (s)	Ref.
Cs ₂ AgBiBr ₆ microsheets	168	1.07	37.2	82.8	This work
CsPbBr ₃ RC	4	1.68	74.4	15.6	55
CsPbBr ₃ cubes	187	1.56	143	320	66
CH ₃ NH ₃ PbI _{3-x} Cl _x thin film	180	3	225	200	17

$$^b \text{Response} = \frac{I_{\text{gas}}}{I_{\text{air}}}$$

Figure S5. (a) FESEM image of Cs₂AgBiBr₆ microsheets at the end of the sensing process. (b) XRD patterns of Cs₂AgBiBr₆ microsheets-based sensor as prepared (black pattern) and after 6 weeks (red pattern). (c-d) XRD patterns as prepared of the microsheets-based sensors as prepared (red pattern) and after its exposure to O₃ gas under relative humidity (blue pattern). The asterisks (*) indicate the reflections of the side phases CsAgBr₂ (PDF #38-0850), AgBr (ICDD 00-006-0438) and Cs₃Bi₂Br₆ (ICDD 01-070-0493) and the rhombus (♦) represents the formation of BiOBr (JCPDS 09-0393) (e) FESEM image of the microsheets after their exposure to RH%.

Figure S6. XPS narrow scans of (a) Cs 3d, (b) Ag 3d, (c) Bi 4f and (d) Br 3d of the Cs₂AgBiBr₆ micro-sheets before and after exposure to O₃. The inset shows the deconvolution of Br 3d orbitals of the as prepared sample with spin orbit splitting of 1.1 eV.

Figure S7. XRD patterns of the microsheets at the end of each annealing/O₃ sensing process. The asterisks correspond to the reflections of the side phases.

Figure S8. Electrical response curves of the microsheets-based sensor for (a) CO₂ and (b) CH₄ detection.

Figure S9. Normalized current curves upon (a) NO, (b) H₂, (c) CH₄ and CO₂ gas exposure of the Cs₂AgBiBr₆ microsheets as a function of time.

Figure S10. XPS narrow scans of (a) Cs 3d, (b) Ag 3d, (c) Bi 4f and (d) Br 3d of the $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ microsheets before and after exposure to gas. The inset shows the deconvolution of Br 3d orbitals of the as prepared sample with spin orbit splitting of 1.1 eV. (e) Survey spectra of H_2 sensors as prepared (lower, black curve) and at the end of the hydrogen process (upper, grey curve) (f) XRD patterns of $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ microsheets-based sensor as prepared (red) and after its exposure to H_2 . The asterisks (*) indicate the reflections of side phases.

DFT calculations

I. Adsorption Energies

Figure S11. The 7-layer slab model with (a) the BiBr/AgBr₃ (TA) termination, and (b) the CsBr termination (TB), viewed along the b-axis in the top and the a-axis in the bottom panels, respectively. The different adsorption site types, i.e., on-top, bridge, hollow, are denoted with yellow stars, diamonds, and circles, respectively.

Figure S12. Adsorption energy in the strongest binding site of each target molecule on the defect-free TA (blue) and TB (green) surface, on the defected TB with V_{Br} (Br-Bi) (magenta) and with V_{Br} (Br-Ag) (violet) surface. The strongest binding sites of each target molecule (i) on the TA surface without defects, (ii) on the TB surface without defects, (iii) on the defected TB surface with V_{Br} (Br-Bi), and on the (iv) defected TB surface with V_{Br} (Br-Ag). Cs, Ag, Bi, Br, O, N, C, and H atoms are illustrated as cyan, silver, purple, brown, red, blue, grey, and white spheres, respectively.

Figure S13. The energetically favorable adsorption sites for the hydrogen molecule on the (a) TA defect-free and defected with V_{Br} , V_{Bi} , V_{Ag} surface, and on the (b) TB defect-free and defected with V_{Br} (Br-Bi) and V_{Br} (Br-Ag), along with their corresponding binding energies in eV. Cs, Ag, Bi, Br, and H atoms are illustrated as cyan, silver, purple, brown, and white spheres, respectively.

Figure S14. The energetically favorable adsorption site for N_2 on the defected TB surface with V_{Br} (Br-Bi), along with the corresponding binding energy in eV. Cs, Ag, Bi, Br, and N atoms are illustrated as cyan, silver, purple, brown, and blue spheres, respectively.

II. Density of States

Figure S15. Partial density of states (PDOS) of the (100) oriented TB $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ model surfaces (a) without defects and (b) defected with V_{Br} (Br-Bi). PDOS of the defected with V_{Br} (Br-Bi) TB surface upon adsorption of (c) CO_2 , and (d) CH_4 .

Upon adsorption of the CO_2 molecules in the vacancy site, the defected states vanish and new distinct states appear around the Fermi level, with contributions from O, Bi and Br atoms being nearly equivalent and C atoms contributing slightly less. On the other hand, the defected states persist in the case of the weakly interacting CH_4 .

III. Charge Density Difference Plots

Figure S16. Charge density difference plots calculated at 0.001 (e/bohr^3) isosurface for (a) O_3 , (b) NO , (c) H_2 , (d) H , (e) CO_2 , and (f) CH_4 adsorbed on the defected TB surface with V_{Br} (Br-Bi). Yellow and cyan areas illustrate charge accumulation and depletion, respectively. Cs, Ag, Bi, Br, O, C, N, and H atoms are illustrated as cyan, silver, purple, brown, red, blue, grey and white spheres, respectively.

In all strongly interacting cases, there is pronounced polarization effect in the upper layers of the surface around the adsorption site, indicative of the rearrangement of the electron density in response to the presence of the adsorbate molecules. At the same time, there is significant polarization of the electron density associated with the adsorbate atoms themselves, suggesting significant charge transfer from the uppermost surface atoms to the adsorbed

molecules. On the other hand, for the weakly interacting H₂ and CH₄ cases, minimal to no polarization effects are observed in the surface and the charge density distribution of the adsorbates remains largely unperturbed.

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